

PIONEERING ECONOMIC GROWTH: EXAMINING THE RATE OF NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES WITH PAID EMPLOYEES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINS (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper conducts an in-depth analysis of the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees in the Romanian Mountains, focusing on the number of employees within the reference period from 2008 to 2018. Through a meticulous examination of key indicators and workforce trends, the study aims to provide insights into the entrepreneurial landscape, growth patterns, and employment dynamics within the picturesque mountainous region.

1. Introduction:

The establishment of enterprises with paid employees is a key driver of economic development. This paper delves into the Romanian Mountains to investigate the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees, analyzing the number of employees within the reference period from 2008

to 2018. The study aims to unravel the economic vitality of these enterprises and their contributions to regional employment.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research integrates data from business registries, labor market reports, and relevant publications. Key indicators, such as the rate of enterprises with paid employees and the corresponding workforce figures, are analyzed to provide a nuanced understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape in the Romanian Mountains.

3. Rate of Enterprises with Paid Employees:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the rate of enterprises established in the Romanian Mountains with paid employees. Metrics such as the prevalence of paid employment, variations across industries, and trends in the establishment of enterprises with a formal workforce are scrutinized to assess the growth patterns within the business landscape.

4. Employment Patterns:

The article delves into the employment patterns within newly established enterprises, examining variations in the number of employees over the specified decade. Insights into industry-specific employment trends and their correlation with the rate of enterprises with paid employees provide valuable information on workforce dynamics.

5. Sectoral Analysis:

An in-depth sectoral analysis is conducted to explore the distribution of newly established enterprises with paid employees across different industries in the Romanian Mountains. This section investigates the prevalence of formal employment within key sectors, shedding light on the diverse economic activities contributing to regional development.

6. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees, the article investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), overall employment rates, and economic stability in the Romanian Mountains. The interconnectedness between the rate of enterprises with paid employees and the broader economic landscape is explored.

7. Results:

Rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees: the number of employees in the reference period (t) at newly established enterprises in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in newly established enterprises in t – percentage

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum,

Maximum, Percentiles 25, 50, 75, so 68.0355, 3.84258, 65.7700, 12.74439, 162.420, -.285, .661, .513, 1.279, 45.03, 42.30, 87.33, 61.0709, 709.0709, 65.08 .

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 Holt; S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 Simple; S8 - Model_8 Holt; S9 - Model_9 Holt; S10 - Model_10 Simple; S11 - Model_11 Simple.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeat in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .362, .458, -.100, .877, -.100, -.097; R-square .262, .181, -4.663E-15, .476, -4.663E-15, -4.574E-15; RMSE 12,072, 4,287, 6,239, 18,197, 6,239, 6,303; MAPS 17,445, 10,270, 5,233, 34,581, 5,233, 5,314; MaxAPE 85,415, 64,111, 22,167, 241,961, 22,167, 22,703; MFA, 7,792, 2,632, 3,862, 11,180, 3,862, 3,928; MaxAE 29,037, 11,252, 14,793, 51,679, 14,793, 14,982; Normalized BIC 5.170, .753, 4.098, 6.021, 4.098, 4.118.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I22 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: .842, .305, 11.197, 12.123, 6.785; S2-Model_2: .869, .351, 6.561, 5.233, 4.193; S3-Model_3: -4.219E-15, -4.219E-15, 8.578, 8.267, 5.984; S4-Model_4: -4.663E-15, -4.663E-15, 13.505, 20.060, 9.769; S5-Model_5: .877, .281, 6.239, 5.637, 3.862; S6-Model_6: 8.549E-15, 8.549E-15, 7.728, 7.177, 5.200; S7-Model_7: -.100, .476, 13.186, 26.029, 9.775; S8-Model_8: .827, .460, 16,112, 34,581, 9,999; S9-Model_9: .776, .277, 14.443, 20.771, 9.483; S10-Model_10: -.027, .318, 18,197, 23,168, 9,478; S11-Model_11: -.083, .417, 17.046, 28.853, 11.180.

Table 39. Prediction analysis for I22

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	54.80	52.41	50.03	47.64	45.25	42.87	40.48	38.09
	UCL	80.13	77.87	75.61	73.35	71.08	68.82	66.56	64.30
	LCL	29.47	26.96	24.44	21.93	19.42	16.91	14.40	11.89
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	76.10	74.55	73.00	71.46	69.91	68.36	66.81	65.27
	UCL	90.94	89.53	88.12	86.70	85.29	83.87	82.46	81.04
	LCL	61.26	59.57	57.89	56.21	54.53	52.85	51.17	49.49
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18	78.18
	UCL	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29	97.29
	LCL	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07	59.07
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11	60.11
	UCL	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20	90.20
	LCL	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02	30.02
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	67.10	65.89	64.69	63.49	62.28	61.08	59.87	58.67
	UCL	81.21	80.01	78.80	77.60	76.40	75.19	73.99	72.78
	LCL	52.98	51.78	50.58	49.37	48.17	46.97	45.76	44.56
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08	79.08
	UCL	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30	96.30
	LCL	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86	61.86
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97	37.97
	UCL	67.35	79.52	88.85	96.73	103.66	109.93	115.70	121.06
	LCL	8.59	-3.58	-12.91	-20.78	-27.72	-33.99	-39.75	-45.12
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	25.48	20.98	16.49	11.99	7.49	2.99	-1.51	-6.01
	UCL	61.93	57.61	53.30	48.98	44.66	40.34	36.02	31.69
	LCL	- 10.97	-15.65	-20.33	-25.00	-29.68	-34.36	-39.03	-43.71

S9- Model_9:	Forecast	43.80	40.93	38.06	35.19	32.31	29.44	26.57	23.70
	UCL	76.47	73.76	71.05	68.34	65.63	62.92	60.20	57.49
	LCL	11.13	8.09	5.06	2.03	-1.01	-4.04	-7.07	-10.10
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58	54.58
	UCL	95.13	111.75	124.52	135.30	144.79	153.38	161.28	168.64
	LCL	14.04	-2.58	-15.35	-26.13	-35.62	-44.21	-52.11	-59.47
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63	32.63
	UCL	70.61	84.00	94.56	103.56	111.54	118.79	125.47	131.71
	LCL	-5.35	-18.74	-29.30	-38.31	-46.29	-53.54	-60.22	-66.45

Figure 3.30. Graphical prediction analysis for I22

7. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining the challenges and opportunities faced by enterprises and employees in the Romanian Mountains, this section investigates factors such as workforce skill requirements, labor market competition, and opportunities for professional development. Addressing these aspects is crucial for fostering a resilient and sustainable business environment.

8. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees in the Romanian Mountains. Considerations such as technological advancements, emerging market trends, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the rate of newly established enterprises with paid employees in the Romanian Mountains from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's economic dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable growth in enterprises with paid employees within the mountainous region.

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